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**Creating Opportunities for Businesses,
Communities and Mangroves
in the Klang Islands**

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WHY ARE MANGROVES IMPORTANT?

Mangroves, both locally and globally, are economically and ecologically important ecosystems¹. They contribute to businesses and communities by, for example:

- Supporting fisheries and aquaculture resources;
- Provisioning raw materials for building, ornamental resources, medicinal goods;
- Enabling cultural practices, especially by local indigenous communities;
- Protecting coastlines from erosion, storms and floods;
- Removing and storing gases that contribute to climate change.

The benefits provided by mangroves have been valued at an average of US\$4,185 ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ (2007

prices) for their contribution to fisheries, fuel, water and coastal protection². **Malaysia has the 3rd largest area of mangroves globally³,** which supports commercially important local species such as tiger prawns (Udang harimau) and mud crabs (Ketam nipah). If other benefits were also monetised, the value of mangroves would be much higher. **Even small patches of mangroves are important and worth creating and protecting⁴.** Similar mangrove areas at Pulau Kukup and Tanjung Piai are now designated as Ramsar Sites (Wetlands of International Importance), and Kuala Selangor Nature Park, famous for its fireflies, is recognised as an Important Bird Area (IBA) by Birdlife International.

WHAT IS THE ISSUE?

Despite recognition of their importance, **Malaysia continues to lose mangroves at one of the highest rates globally (700-800 ha year⁻¹ between 1990-2017⁵).** The state of Selangor lost 22% (6,424 ha) of its mangrove cover between 1990 and 2010, with further significant loss before this time⁶.

In 1988, the Klang Islands and Carey Island were home to more than 19,000 ha of mangrove forest, but 22% (4,139 ha) of this has also been lost since then: an area approximately the same size as Pulau Indah⁷ (Figure 1).

The loss of mangroves in Selangor and the Klang Islands is mainly due to land conversion for urban development (ports, housing, light industry) and oil palm plantations. Erosion, aquaculture, pollution, sand dredging and increasing wake from shipping traffic along with a rising sea level have also contributed to a squeeze on mangrove fringes around the islands^{8,9,10,11,16}.

Figure 1: Areas of mangrove loss (red) and mangrove gain (green) on the Klang Islands and Carey Island, 1988 - 2018.

WHY IS THIS ISSUE SO SIGNIFICANT?

The loss of mangroves is known to **increase flooding** during high tides and erosion along the coast^{7,13,14,15}, as well as **affect local fisheries resources, productivity of agricultural land and cultural practices**. Consequently, the livelihoods of local communities are impacted through **loss of employment options and related income**, and **local infrastructure is affected by erosion and flooding**^{7,9,16}.

Opportunities for the expansion of tourism and aquaculture, alongside the maintenance of existing fisheries activities and cultural practices may be lost or reduced^{7,9}. Outside of permanent reserves, mangrove protection is inadequately addressed by existing forestry, land-use and fisheries policies and regulations, resulting in a lack of control of anthropogenic impacts on mangroves^{8,12}.

WHY ARE CURRENT POLICIES FAILING MANGROVES?

There are a number of reasons why national and local policies are failing to protect mangroves including:

The interconnectedness between sectors (e.g. fisheries, environment, coastal protection, port industries, communities, local development and climate change) and mangroves appears to be largely unrecognised and **the importance of mangroves is undervalued** by decision-makers^{2,7,9}.

The Draft Local Plan of Majlis Perbandaran Klang (MPKLP) 2035 (Replacement) acknowledges that **developments tend not to follow Lembaga Urus Air Selangor (LUAS) guidelines** such as the creation of 400m natural buffer zones. Consequently, there has been degradation of natural resources and unauthorized development in agricultural areas¹⁷.

State Authorities are able to approve developments which are contrary to adopted local authority plans, or vice versa, with restricted opportunities for appeals¹⁸.

There are **few incentives to prevent private and state landowners from treating mangrove areas as land banks for future development**.

Mangrove management and conservation is administered by multiple government agencies with overlapping or conflicting aims and responsibilities. These include the Forestry Department of Peninsula Malaysia, which takes state level decisions on forest resources and gazetting; the Department of Irrigation and Drainage with national responsibilities for flood and coastal zone management; and the

Department of Fisheries Malaysia, which only focuses on fisheries resources and not the ecosystems from which they are derived (except within marine parks that fall under its jurisdiction). Across Peninsular Malaysia, this **sectoral approach has led to fragmented management and poorly integrated land-use policy directions**^{7,8,12,19}.

The drivers of change impacting mangroves span areas of responsibility across agencies. For example, the Department of Environment has federal responsibility for monitoring and enforcement of environmental quality legislation and guidance, including water pollution from shipping and port activities. Also at the federal level are the Port Authorities, including the Klang Port Authority, which has administrative jurisdiction over port development on the islands. These interests compete with state level land-use decision-making⁷.

Implementation of existing state by-laws and national policies at the state level are weakly enforced. For example, the principles of the revised National Forestry Policy 1992 to move from a focus on sustainable yields toward an emphasis on sound management, conservation, utilisation, development and protection of mangroves in Malaysia, have been inconsistently applied and vary on a site-to-site basis²⁰.

Despite recognition of the importance of community-based management in the 10th Malaysia Plan 2011-2015 and its establishment globally^{21,22}, **a tradition of top-down approaches to resource management leaves little room for community engagement and empowerment**.

HOW CAN THE SITUATION BE CHANGED?

Through extensive stakeholder engagement and interaction with communities, the NetComFish project has identified a number of ways in which mangrove management can be improved for the Klang Islands. This can be achieved through the enforcement of existing policies as well as the exploration of new policies and approaches. Implementing this approach could provide an effective test case for mangrove management elsewhere in Malaysia.

Mangrove management and conservation on the Klang Islands must be implemented through a multisectoral, collaborative, and ecosystem-based approach coordinated on the basis of national, state, and, perhaps most importantly, local strategies. Existing cooperation between agencies, for example through programmes such as the Integrated Coastal Management Plan and the Ecosystem Approach to Fisheries Management (EFM), should be strengthened by a participatory management framework including local communities and businesses alongside local and state officials. **A joint management committee should have responsibility for management planning, implementation and enforcement, and should include local community representatives.** One agency should be given responsibility for granting and controlling use of mangrove areas *and* their management.

The inclusion of the Klang Islands' mangroves as an Environmentally Sensitive Area (ESA) in Malaysia's Third National Physical Plan (post 2020), and the Draft Local Plan of Majlis Perbandaran Klang (MPKLP) 2035 (Replacement) (Klang Municipal Council (2019) should be closely monitored, and potentially conflicting proposals and developments highlighted. The local council should adopt a zoning approach to the control of its mangrove forests, with clearly laid out permissions and prohibitions allocated to each zone.

The State government should adopt a 'no net loss' approach to development proposals affecting mangrove sites, incorporating a standard framework for businesses to engage in mangrove replanting to redress and offset any losses identified. This can be achieved by revising national planning policy frameworks to explicitly reflect a 'no net loss' approach for proposals impacting mangrove forests and other sensitive habitats. Where mangrove loss or degradation is unavoidable, accepted developments should

include clauses requiring businesses to replace mangrove losses with new planting and follow LUAS's guidelines respecting 400m coastal buffer zones. Agreements should also require businesses to monitor and manage new mangrove plantings to ensure seedling survival.

Loopholes in relevant legislation and enforcement responsibilities should be closed to allow agencies to afford greater protection to mangroves. For example, providing more power to forestry officials to penalise unlicensed tree cutting at source, and enabling fisheries officials to take action against both mangrove *and* fishing activities taking place within the 1 nautical mile limit of the coastline in Selangor (possibly amending the Fisheries Act 1985, as already amended by the 2012 Act). **The most effective way to close all loopholes would be to gazette all mangrove sites on the islands not already designated as forest reserves to strengthen legal protection within the remit of the Forestry Act 1984.** Such an act should also extend the current 25-year state-wide moratorium on logging activities within Forest Reserves to a broader area.

The non-market values of mangroves in the Klang Islands should be estimated to heighten recognition of the value that mangroves afford to the delivery of local, national and global strategic objectives. For example, to the Draft Local Plan of Majlis Perbandaran Klang (MPKLP) 2035 (Replacement), the National Forestry Policy 1978 (revised 1992) and National Forestry Act 1984 (revised 1993)²⁰, the National Fisheries Act 1985, as well as the National Policy on Biological Diversity 2016-25, the National Wetlands Policy (currently in revision), and contributions to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Cost-benefit analyses that capture both environmental and economic interests will provide evidence to support local decision-making without jeopardising mangrove health.

The private sector and local communities should be encouraged to engage in initiatives that protect and enhance mangroves. This could be achieved by incentivising nature-based solutions in future planning⁷, reducing carbon footprints, and developing climate change adaptation plans, as well as through directed Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programmes to provide ongoing support for mangrove-based activities.

Tree planting CSR activities by different organisations should be strategically coordinated by NGOs, linked to internal KPIs, guided by sound science, and accompanied by subsequent monitoring and protection. Proper activity records will provide the state assemblyman with numbers and costings, and aid in assessing the success of these planting schemes. Local communities should be able to volunteer to monitor planning and legislative policies and be awarded formal authority by the State to carry out monitoring tasks and provide feedback reports.

Incentives should be provided for nature-based solutions that incorporate mangroves to, for example, provide soft engineering options to reduce the vulnerability of sites subject to erosion and coastal flooding from high tides and storm surges. Such solutions will need to be integrated into and between various strategies and plans, including National Security Council Directive No. 20 (Policy and Mechanism on National Disaster and Relief Management) (1997), the National Policy on Climate Change 2009, the forthcoming Climate Change Act and associated adaptation and mitigation plans, and the Environmental Quality Act 1974 (as amended 2000). Development of vulnerability assessment methods for disaster risk reduction needs to progress²³, and the role of nature-based solutions within them reviewed. The release of land-banked mangrove areas could be incentivised through innovative ecotourism options.

To be successful, **new approaches to mangrove management must be aligned to various strategic aims.** For example, those of sustainable green growth, land use planning, natural capital accounting, biodiversity protection, inclusiveness, and environmental tourism as per, for example, the 11th Malaysia Plan, National Forestry Policy, across all dimensions of the draft MPKLP 2035 (Replacement), and the National Policy on Biological Diversity (NPBD) 2016-25. The effective, inclusive management and protection of mangroves also has a role to play in Malaysia's progress towards the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

About NetComFish

The NetComFish project was a two-and-a-half-year collaboration between the University of Malaya and Plymouth Marine Laboratory, funded by the Newton Ungku-Omar Fund grant number IF021-2017 and NE/P020925/1. The project has three main aims:

1. To explore the interlinkages between fisheries, mangroves and communities to advance the sustainable management fishery and mangrove resources.
2. To set the foundation for multi-stakeholder management of the mangrove ecosystem and its dependent resources such as fisheries.
3. To develop a program of environmental education emphasizing the importance of mangroves.

The NetComFish team have been successful in acquiring follow-on funding for this work in the form of the NexAMS project: Nexus Action for Mangroves in Selangor, funded through the Newton Fund Impact Scheme.

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